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ABSTRACT

This is a report for design process of radial turbine used in turbocharger. Input for design requirements are power, mass flow rate, inlet temperature, pressure and rotation speed. The design variables include rotor radius ratios, stator-exit angle and rotor-exit tangential velocity distribution. The geometry was tested using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) where some modifications were introduced on the preliminary design to satisfy the design requirements. The turbine's design point rotational speed is 60000 rpm, stagnation inlet temperature and pressure are 1050K, 3.39 bar respectively and mass flow rate is 0.55kg/s. The turbine rotor has 15 blades with inlet and exit diameters 102mm and 36 mm.

KEYWORDS: Analytical design of turbine, circular arc method, Radial turbine, Turbocharger.**INTRODUCTION**

There are basically two types of turbine which are radial flow and axial flow. A radial turbine appears similar to the centrifugal compressor but the diffuser vanes are replaced by a ring of nozzle guide vanes. A radial turbine is a turbine in which the working fluid enters radially i.e. radial to the shaft. There are two types of radial flow turbines which are inward flow radial turbines and outward flow radial turbines. The gas flow in radial flow turbine is tangential with high velocity and is directed inwards and leaves the rotor with a small whirl velocity near the axis of rotation. The radial turbine handles low mass flows more efficiently than the axial flow turbine. For this reason the radial flow turbines has been widely used in the cryogenic industry as turbo expander and also in turbochargers for reciprocating engines. The radial turbine which has variable-area stator can engage over a broad flow range at nearly constant pressure ratio, temperature and speed. If this can be achieved at high efficiency, the turbine can contribute to high engine performance over the entire operating range. But the stator-area variation along with the associated vane-end clearances affects the turbine performance and these effects must be taken into consideration for proper prediction of engine performance. In radial turbine larger pressure and temperature drops can be achieved in single stage compared to an axial turbine, so radial turbine can extract larger work in a single stage. A Turbine for a 75KW micro gas turbine has been designed as a part of the project. The analysis of the system involves many repetitive calculations of component performance and geometry over a range of conditions.

DESIGN METHODOLOGY

The descriptive process mentioned below are used for designing the radial turbine where the numbers of turbine blades are decided using trial and error method. The power required by the compressor in the turbocharger is produced in the radial turbine. The stagnation temperature and the mass flow rate are the values generally taken from a automobile engine. The standard values ratio of the shroud to inlet radius and exit hub to shroud radius are used.

Construction of vane profile

From thermodynamic design all dimensional parameter like inlet and outlet vane angle, radii at tip and root, blade height are obtained. For the vane profile work circular arc method has been used. Under circular arc method the circle is divided into number of circle having equal interval, starting with outermost circle with given angle found in the design a curve is drawn up to the internal circle. Both root and tip curves can be obtained by this method.

Figure 1 Profile by Circular Arc Method

3D model

Now we can create the 3D model using CATIA software. Different view are shown below

Figure 2 Various Views of Turbine

Table 1 input and output parameters

Sr. No.	Input Parameters	Values	Sr. No.	Output Parameters	Values
1)	Input Power	75kW	1)	α_1	75.04 ⁰
2)	Number of vanes	15	2)	β_1	29.92 ⁰
3)	Inlet Temperature	1050 K	3)	Mach number at inlet	0.5106
4)	Mass Flow Rate	0.55 kg/s	4)	Axial velocity of air	215 m/s
5)	Volumetric efficiency	83%	5)	Whirling velocity of air	804.66 m/s
6)	Υ	1.4	6)	Depth of blade at inlet	8.16 mm
7)	Exit hub to shroud radius ratio	0.4	7)	Radius of hub at outlet	15 mm
8)	Shroud to inlet radius ratio	0.7	8)	Radius of shroud at outlet	36 mm
9)	Rotation Speed of Turbine	60000 rpm			

CONCLUSION

The thermal analysis of turbine and the geometric parameter are calculated for geometric modeling. And this results can be use to analysis and manufacturing of turbocharger.

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